

A Needs Analysis Study of Novice EFL Teachers' Professional Development in Türkiye

Gizem AKÇOR¹ & Hatice ERGÜL²

¹ İzmir Bakırçay University, İzmir, TÜRKİYE
gizemakcor@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0001-5997-1029

² Hacettepe University, Ankara, TÜRKİYE

hatice.ergul@hacettepe.edu.tr

ORCID: 0000-0002-0494-432X

Article information

Submission	02/01/2025	Revision received	04/04/2025
Acceptance	11/04/2025	Publication date	24/04/2025

Keywords:

Novice EFL teachers

Professional development

Challenges

Induction program

Learning to teach

Abstract: This study investigates the professional development needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye, incorporating perspectives from multiple stakeholders. Additionally, it evaluates novice teachers' perceptions of the induction program prepared for novice teachers by the Turkish Ministry of National Education (MoNE). Data collected from 109 participants (29 novice EFL teachers, 55 experienced EFL teachers, and 25 EFL teacher educators) through questionnaires suggest that while the program supports novice teachers in adapting to the profession, its overall effectiveness remains limited. The study identifies key areas for improvement, including the selection of mentors, the reduction of administrative workload, and the enhancement of practical training. The findings of the study, supported by the literature, emphasize the need for a more tailored professional development program that incorporates critical elements such as well-being, classroom management, technology-integrated materials development, diversity in EFL classrooms, and reflective practice. The implications of this study provide valuable insights for policymakers and teacher educators seeking to improve the induction process for novice teachers.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Mesleğe yeni başlayan öğretmenler

Yabancı dil olarak İngilizce

Mesleki gelişim

Zorluklar

Öğretmeyi öğrenme

Türkiye'de Mesleğe Yeni Başlayan İngilizce Öğretmenlerinin Mesleki Gelişim İhtiyaçları Üzerine Bir İhtiyaç Analizi Çalışması

Özet: Bu çalışma, Türkiye'de mesleğe yeni başlayan İngilizce öğretmenlerinin mesleki gelişim ihtiyaçlarını, farklı paydaşların görüşlerini dikkate alarak incelemektedir. Ayrıca, Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı (MEB) tarafından uygulanan aday öğretmen yetiştirme programı hakkındaki mesleğe yeni başlayan öğretmenlerin algılarını değerlendirmektedir. Araştırmacı tarafından geliştirilen anketler aracılığıyla 29 mesleğe yeni başlayan İngilizce öğretmeni, 55 deneyimli İngilizce öğretmeni ve 25 öğretmen eğitimci olmak üzere toplam 109 katılımcıdan elde edilen veriler, programın eğitim-öğretim yönetmelikleri ve mevzuat hakkında önemli bilgiler sunduğunu, ancak genel etkinliğinin sınırlı olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Çalışma, mentor seçiminde iyileştirmeler yapılması, idari yüklerin hafifletilmesi ve uygulamalı eğitimin güçlendirilmesi gibi geliştirilmesi gereken temel alanları belirlemektedir. Ayrıca, bulgular, literatürle desteklenerek, öğrenci refahı, sınıf yönetimi, teknoloji entegreli materyal geliştirme, İngilizce sınıflarında çeşitlilik ve yansıtıcı uygulama gibi önemli unsurları içeren daha özelleştirilmiş bir mesleki gelişim programına duyulan ihtiyacı vurgulamaktadır. Bu sonuçlar, mesleğe yeni başlayan öğretmenlerin öğretmenlik mesleğine başlama sürecini iyileştirmek isteyen politika yapıcılar ve öğretmen eğitimcileri için bir takım önemli önerilerde bulunmaktadır.

To Cite This Article: Akçor, G., & Ergül, H. (2025). A needs analysis study of novice EFL teachers' professional development in Türkiye. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 19(1), 117–136. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15210710>

1. Introduction

In-service teaching differs considerably from pre-service teaching (Farrell, 2006). The transition from being a student teacher to becoming a full-fledged teacher is abrupt and significant. Teachers at the beginning of their careers with limited teaching experience are often labeled as 'novice' or early career teachers, beginning teachers, or newly qualified teachers. The number of years a teacher must work before losing the "novice" label remains unclear and varies among scholars. For example, Kim and Roth (2011) define novice teachers as those with less than five years of teaching experience, while Farrell (2012) argues that a teacher with more than three years of experience should no longer be classified as a novice. This study adopts Farrell's (2012) definition and considers novices with a maximum of three years of teaching experience. Regardless of the number of years, the ideals that novice teachers develop during their teacher education are overshadowed by the realities of school life. The outcome is a sense of "reality shock" (Veenman, 1984) as they realize that applying the concepts learned in their university programs is more challenging than expected, and they are inadequately prepared for their duties.

The shift from theory to practice, combined with the daily demands of teaching, presents challenges for novice teachers, making their transition into the profession even more challenging (Stewart & Jansky, 2022). This transition bringing numerous challenges such as demanding workloads, ambiguous expectations, insufficient resources, isolation, and a 'sink and swim' attitude in schools (Anhorn, 2008) can greatly affect novice teachers' long-term job satisfaction, professional competence, growth, and longevity in the teaching profession (Hebert & Worthy, 2001). Novice teachers are expected to take on the same responsibilities, challenges, and heavy workloads as experienced teachers; yet, unlike their more experienced colleagues, they lack prior teaching experience to rely on and get minimal formal support (Anhorn, 2008; Fantilli & McDougall, 2009; Farrell, 2012, 2016; Hebert & Worthy, 2001). New teachers have two jobs: "They have to teach, and they have to learn to teach" (Feiman-Nemser, 2001, p. 18). Armed with theoretical knowledge of their subject, a handful of teaching strategies, and basic planning abilities, novice teachers often go through a roller-coaster of emotions, filled with excitement, frustration, confusion, feelings of isolation, and self-doubt (Farrell, 2016; Hebert & Worthy, 2001; Zepeda & Mayers, 2001). As they navigate challenging circumstances alone, some struggle with loneliness (Anhorn, 2008), others find their jobs "frustrating, unrewarding and intolerably difficult" (Fantilli & McDougall, 2009, p. 814), and some ultimately leave the profession early in their careers (Farrell, 2012).

A growing body of research (e.g., Çakmak et al., 2018; Ergünay & Adıgüzel, 2019; Fantilli & McDougall, 2009; Kozikoğlu & Senemoğlu, 2018; Stewart & Jansky, 2022) has consistently highlighted the multifaceted challenges novice teachers encounter during their early years in the profession. These challenges can be categorized into six key areas. First, instructional difficulties include managing classroom discipline, addressing student motivation, differentiating instruction for diverse learners, teaching students with special needs, adapting instructional techniques, implementing effective assessment practices, and coping with limited resources, time constraints, and management. Second, relational challenges emerge in interactions with parents, colleagues, administrators, and mentors, often complicating teachers' professional integration. Third, professional and institutional barriers hinder teachers' growth, such as insufficient mentoring, lack of institutional support, ineffective pre-service training, limited professional development opportunities, and a pervasive sense of isolation. Fourth, adaptation challenges arise as novice teachers transition into the school environment, profession, and society while striving to balance personal and professional

responsibilities. Fifth, excessive workload remains a persistent concern, contributing to stress and burnout. Finally, emotional challenges, particularly in managing stress, further exacerbate the difficulties faced in the early years of teaching.

Although research on the challenges novice teachers face is extensive, studies explicitly examining the difficulties novice EFL teachers encounter remain relatively limited. However, the literature (e.g., Chaaban & Du, 2017; Farrell, 2003, 2016; Lomi & Mbato, 2020; Septiani et al., 2019; Widiati et al., 2018) identifies several key challenges. Student-related difficulties, including classroom management issues, lack of student motivation, negative attitudes toward English, individual differences, and large class sizes, often hinder effective instruction. Additionally, administrative and workload pressures—such as excessive teaching and assessment responsibilities, time-consuming lesson planning, unrealistic expectations from schools and parents, and insufficient administrative support—contribute to teacher stress. Pedagogically, novice EFL teachers frequently struggle with inadequate preparation, difficulties in translating theory into practice, adapting instructional methods, and managing the demands of standardized exams and high-stakes testing. The absence of sufficient mentorship, induction programs, and collegial collaboration further exacerbates these challenges, limiting professional growth. Moreover, socio-cultural and identity-related difficulties, including developing a professional identity, workplace politics, and discrepancies between expectations and reality, add to the complexity of early-career teaching experiences. Psychological and emotional struggles—such as transition shock, self-efficacy concerns, job dissatisfaction, burnout, and isolation—significantly affect teachers' well-being and retention, too. Finally, communication difficulties with parents present additional barriers.

The specific challenges novice EFL teachers face, particularly in Türkiye, have received even less scholarly attention. A brief outline of the teacher recruitment and induction program in Türkiye is provided to address this gap. Eligible candidates, who are graduates of education faculties and graduates from other faculties with a teaching certificate, must pass a two-stage centralized examination for teaching positions in state schools. This process includes a written exam, followed by an oral exam requiring a minimum score of 60. Appointments are based on overall ranking, and newly appointed teachers must complete a one-year induction program. Successful completion of this program marks the end of their induction period. The process has undergone several revisions, with the most recent update in 2016 introducing a 26-week induction program that includes in-class, in-school, and out-of-school activities and in-service training. Various researchers have studied how novice teachers work under mentor supervision and participate in administrative tasks. Çelik and Atik (2020) reviewed 14 studies. They found that while the program was generally well-received in content and structure, issues arose in its implementation, mentoring, seminars, evaluations, and paperwork. Similarly, İlyas et al. (2017) showed that most teachers rated the program positively for preparing them for the profession. However, all agreed on the need for mentoring and paperwork process improvements. Ekinci et al. (2019) found that beginning teachers felt the program did not provide the expected competencies, citing issues like insufficient program information, excessive paperwork, and problems with mentor selection and training.

Likewise, Kozikoğlu and Soyalp (2018) reported that while the program helped with understanding institutional culture, administrative tasks, and parent communication, there were ongoing difficulties with mentoring, form completion, and information dissemination. Despite its theoretical strengths, practical challenges remained. While previous studies

highlight the program's strengths and weaknesses, they rarely focus on novice EFL teachers, signaling a need for further research specific to their experiences and needs. One of the few studies that attempt to shed light on this issue is Akçor and Savaşçı (2020), who conducted a qualitative systematic review to explore the challenges faced by novice EFL teachers in Turkey. Following predefined inclusion criteria, they analyzed a total of nine studies in detail (i.e., Akcan, 2016; Bekdemir, 2019; Bulut Albaba, 2017; Gok Kaca & Yigitoglu, 2017; Güngör et al., 2019; Karataş & Karaman, 2013; Öztürk & Yıldırım, 2012; Sali & Kecik, 2018; Yazan, 2016). These studies collectively identify several recurring challenges. Instructionally, novice teachers encounter difficulties in lesson planning, teaching strategies, classroom management, student motivation, communicative language teaching, addressing diverse student needs, and supporting low-proficiency learners. Curriculum-related obstacles, such as rigid syllabi, limited flexibility, the constraints of high-stakes exams, and misalignment between syllabus objectives and assessment methods, further hinder their effectiveness. Additionally, restricted access to professional development opportunities and inadequate collegial support create further growth barriers. Social adaptation poses another significant challenge as teachers navigate complex relationships with students, colleagues, administrators, and parents while contending with hierarchical pressures, workplace mobbing, and oppressive attitudes. Psychologically, feelings of isolation, lack of appreciation, and inadequate institutional support exacerbate these difficulties, making professional integration even more demanding.

Although numerous studies have highlighted the various challenges novice teachers encounter, limited research has focused on strategies or recommendations for addressing these difficulties (Akçor & Savaşçı, 2020; Çakmak et al., 2019). The studies analyzed by Akçor and Savaşçı (2020) put forward several recommendations regarding in-service teacher training. One of the most frequently suggested strategies is enhancing induction programs and professional development opportunities for novice teachers. Much of what is written about novice teachers has also raised a grave concern over the need for professional development to successfully navigate the initial phase of their teaching career (Hong, 2012; Zhukova, 2018). Stewart et al. (2020) found that the disconnect between the theories teacher candidates learn in their education programs and the policies and teaching methods they are expected to follow in practice can lead them to doubt their ability to succeed. This dissonance contributes to the growing issue of teacher attrition. Professional development programs can play a vital role in supporting novice teachers by helping them critically reflect on their pedagogical beliefs, refine their instructional approaches, and navigate challenges on their path to success (Smith & Ingersoll, 2004). In his study, Farrell (2006) also argues that language teacher education programs have traditionally focused on teaching methods, often neglecting the more profound understanding of what it truly means to be a language teacher. He suggests that these programs should shift their emphasis from various teaching methods to developing skills in anticipatory reflection, helping novice teachers better understand the challenges they will face when transitioning from teacher education to actual classroom environments. In this regard, professional development programs based on novices' needs can act as "a bridge, enabling the student of teaching to become a teacher of students" (Smith & Ingersoll, 2004, p. 683). In their study, Kennedy and McKay (2011) draw significant attention to this issue, referring to Wilson et al.'s (2006) research, which reviewed 3,500 articles on teachers' continuous professional development. They found out, however, that only 13 of these specifically focused on early professional development.

Wilson et al. (2006) highlight that, aside from their report, there is a significant lack of research addressing the specific needs of teachers in the post-induction phase. Moreover,

little effort has been made to determine the types of support that novice teachers find most beneficial. Considering that novice teachers have diverse academic and personal backgrounds and varying philosophies, beliefs, skills, and knowledge that influence their professional growth and performance, adequate support should go beyond simply providing professional development opportunities. Instead, it is essential to offer structured and differentiated professional development tailored to their specific developmental stage, training background, and support needs. (Kennedy & McKay, 2011; Zhukova, 2018). Supporting this view, the results of Zorba's (2022) study reaffirm that generic, decontextualized in-service training is ineffective for teacher development and emphasize the need for long-term, context-specific induction programs that support needs-based professional development. Zein (2017) also emphasizes that previous studies have explored the challenges teachers encounter in the classroom and various pedagogical concerns and examined specific professional development programs and activities. However, a gap remains in identifying and addressing teachers' professional development needs.

Stewart and Jansky (2022) provide a different perspective and found that mentorship in induction programs does not always provide the intended support for novice teachers. Their study highlighted the case of one of the participants, whose frustration stemmed from a toxic rather than productive relationship with her assigned mentor. Despite rumors that she was not performing her job correctly, her mentor neither checked in on her nor helped her improve. This finding underscores the complexity of teacher relationships within schools and suggests that mentorship can be beneficial but ineffective. Given these circumstances, online professional development programs may offer a more reliable alternative by providing structured, consistent support for novice teachers—one of the key motivations behind this study.

In a nutshell, this study primarily investigated the professional development needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye by drawing insights from multiple stakeholders, providing a comprehensive understanding of the support novice EFL teachers require. In doing so, it also explored novice EFL teachers' perceptions of the teacher induction program implemented by the Turkish MoNE. That being said, this study is significant on many grounds. First, while a substantial body of research has explored the challenges faced by novice teachers, studies specifically investigating their professional development needs—particularly those of novice EFL teachers in the Turkish context—remain scarce. This study contributes to the existing literature by addressing this critical gap. Another significant contribution of this study is its comprehensive perspective. In this regard, it stands apart from earlier studies that primarily examined challenges and gathered data only from one or two stakeholder groups, as this study gathers insights from multiple stakeholders. Most importantly, the study's findings can potentially inform key educational stakeholders, guiding future teacher training and support improvements.

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What are novice EFL teachers' perspectives on the current induction program implemented by the Turkish MoNE?
2. What are the perspectives of novice EFL teachers, experienced teachers, and EFL teacher educators on the professional development needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

The current study employs a descriptive exploratory qualitative design, complemented by descriptive statistical data, to understand the professional development needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye. Qualitative research is well-suited for studies exploring complex contexts or settings where participants engage with a problem or topic (Creswell & Poth, 2018). This research design enables an in-depth examination of the factors influencing novice EFL teachers' professional growth, drawing on multiple perspectives from various stakeholders to ensure a holistic understanding of the issue. Additionally, descriptive statistical data were incorporated to support qualitative findings by offering a broader overview of trends and patterns observed among the participants. Findings of this research serve as the basis for designing, implementing, and evaluating a needs-based online professional development program.

2.2. Setting and Participants

The research was conducted online, where participants completed a digital questionnaire designed to explore the perceived professional development needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye. A non-probability sampling method, commonly used in qualitative research, was employed to select participants. Purposive sampling (Cohen et al., 2018) was used to ensure participants met predefined criteria aligned with the study's aims, enabling the researchers to gather insights from individuals with relevant experience and knowledge. Data were collected from 109 participants: 29 novice EFL teachers (24 female, five male) with less than three years of teaching experience; 55 experienced EFL teachers (42 female, 13 male) with 5 to 10+ years of experience; and 25 EFL teacher educators (19 female, six male) with 5 to 30+ years of experience. This diverse sample provided a wide range of perspectives on the professional development needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye.

2.3. Data Collection Tools

For the present study, data were collected using researcher-designed questionnaires tailored to three distinct participant groups—each questionnaire aimed to gather insights into the professional development needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye. The novice EFL teacher questionnaire consisted of four sections—the first section collected demographic information. The second section was adapted from Öztürk's (2008) Questionnaire for Novice Teachers, a validated Likert-scale instrument with five components: (1) personal information; (2) job-related concerns (e.g., workload, instructional challenges, and classroom management); (3) social concerns (e.g., relationships with students, parents, colleagues, supervisors, and mentors, and social status and identity); (4) perceptions of pre-service training; and (5) perceptions of in-service training. This adaptation was justified due to its alignment with the study's objectives. It demonstrated reliability (Cronbach's alpha ranging from .88 to .94). The third section contained eight open-ended questions, one adapted from Salı's (2008) questionnaire. The fourth section included two questions: one requiring participants to rate their perceived support needs and another open-ended question.

The experienced EFL teacher questionnaire was structured into three sections: the first for demographic data, the second with four open-ended questions about early teaching experiences, and the third with two questions on the perceived support needs of novice Turkish EFL teachers—one rating item and one open-ended question. The EFL teacher

educator questionnaire also had three sections: the first for demographic data, the second with four open-ended questions about early teaching experiences, and the third with four questions on the perceived professional needs of novice Turkish EFL teachers—three open-ended and one rating item based on perceived support needs. The researcher developed all open-ended questions and rating items assessing perceived support needs in the final sections of each questionnaire. They were informed by a comprehensive literature review on novice teacher challenges, support needs, and induction experiences, ensuring their relevance to the study's objectives.

2.4. Data Collection Procedure

Data for this study were collected through an online questionnaire administered to three participant groups. The questionnaire began with an introductory section outlining its purpose, assuring participants that their responses would remain confidential and be used solely for research purposes. Participants were required to check a consent box before proceeding to ensure ethical compliance. The researcher also provided her email address for any participant inquiries or clarifications. Before distribution, the questionnaire underwent expert review by two specialists in the field, and revisions were made based on their feedback. The final version of the questionnaire was administered during the fall term of the 2021–2022 academic year.

2.5. Data Analysis

This study's qualitative data analysis followed Creswell and Creswell's (2018) structured, sequential approach. The process began with data organization, including transcription and sorting, followed by an initial review to gain a general understanding before coding the data into meaningful units. Themes and descriptions were then generated, including multiple perspectives and supporting evidence. An inter-coder agreement process was used to enhance reliability, where two independent researchers reviewed and compared the coding results. For the structured sections of the questionnaire with Likert-scale and rating items, descriptive statistics—precisely frequencies and percentages—were applied to summarize participants' responses, providing an overview of trends and complementing the qualitative findings.

3. Findings

This section presents the research findings based on the study's research questions. The first question examines novice EFL teachers' perceptions of the induction program implemented by the Turkish MoNE, while the second investigates the professional development needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, highlight key trends alongside thematic analysis and identify recurring patterns, challenges, and areas for improvement. The findings are organized according to each research question for a clear and systematic presentation of the data.

3.1. The Novice EFL Teachers' Perceptions of the Induction Program

All novice EFL teachers participating in the study (n=29) attended the induction program by the Turkish MoNE. The third section of the questionnaire focused on exploring participants' perceptions of the program. Specifically, the second question in this section sought to identify the types of professional support they received before eliciting their opinions on the program. As shown in Table 1, the findings reveal the extent of

engagement in various induction activities. The most reported forms of support included attending conferences, seminars, or courses for novice teachers (89.7%) and receiving collegial support (82.8%). Additionally, a significant majority (79.3%) were informed about school policies and rules. Nearly half of the participants reported observing experienced teachers' classes (48.3%) and being assigned a formal mentor in their field (44.8%). Furthermore, 37.9% stated that an experienced EFL teacher had observed them, and 34.5% attended formal school meetings and received information about the foreign language education curriculum. However, fewer participants reported access to additional resources or accommodations, with only 27.6% utilizing materials designed for novice teachers and 20.7% given fewer responsibilities beyond teaching duties. Moreover, only 17.2% collaborated on lesson planning with colleagues, and even fewer (13.8%) had a reduced teaching load.

Table 1.

Professional support during the induction program

Forms of Professional Support	N	f	%
I have attended conferences/seminars/courses held for novice EFL teachers.	29	26	89.7
I have got collegial support and help.	29	24	82.8
I have been informed about school policies and rules.	29	23	79.3
I have observed classes of experienced teachers at my school.	29	14	48.3
I have been assigned a formal mentor from your field.	29	13	44.8
An experienced EFL teacher observed me.	29	11	37.9
I have been informed about the curriculum of foreign language education.	29	10	34.5
I attended formal meetings held at school.	29	10	34.5
I have drawn on materials written for novice EFL teachers.	29	8	27.6
I have been given fewer responsibilities other than my subject field.	29	6	20.7
I have prepared joint lesson plans with the other EFL teachers.	29	5	17.2
I have been given fewer classes to teach.	29	4	13.8

Table 2 outlines the participants' perceived strengths and limitations of the induction program. Many respondents (f = 9) reported no perceived strengths. The most frequently cited positive aspect was the program's role in providing information about regulations and school policies (f = 6). Online accessibility (f = 3) was also recognized as a strength, along with guidance from mentors, theoretical knowledge, and support for adapting to the profession (f = 3 each). Opportunities for networking and peer support (f = 2) were also mentioned, though less commonly.

In contrast, the program's limitations were more pronounced. The most frequently reported issue was insufficient and ineffective training (f = 9), with participants noting a lack of depth and practical relevance in the content. Excessive paperwork and procedural burdens (f = 6) were significant concerns, with teachers feeling overwhelmed by unnecessary documentation. Fatigue and workload issues (f = 5) were shared as participants struggled to balance program demands with teaching responsibilities. The ineffectiveness of the online format (f = 4) was another challenge, seen as less engaging and interactive. Additionally, the lack of subject-specific mentoring and training (f = 3) was noted, as some teachers were assigned mentors from different disciplines, thereby limiting the relevance of guidance. Finally, participants highlighted the need for more practical application and classroom experience (f = 3), advocating for more hands-on training and direct classroom observations. These findings suggest that while the program offers some benefits, significant improvements are needed to enhance its effectiveness.

Table 2.
The perceived strengths and limitations of the induction program

Categories	Codes	N	f
Strengths	No perceived strengths	29	9
	Providing information about regulations and school policies	29	6
	Online accessibility	29	3
	Guidance from mentors	29	3
	Providing theoretical knowledge	29	3
	Facilitating adaptation to the profession	29	3
	Opportunities for networking and peer support	29	2
Limitations	Insufficient and ineffective training	29	9
	Excessive paperwork and procedural burden	29	6
	Fatigue and workload issues	29	5
	Ineffectiveness of online format	29	4
	Lack of subject-specific mentoring and training	29	3
	Lack of practical application and real classroom experience	29	3

Table 3 presents the suggested changes to the induction program based on participant responses. One of the most frequently mentioned suggestions was replacing trainers and modifying training methods ($f = 6$), with participants advocating for selecting more knowledgeable trainers and shifting from passive seminar-based instruction to more interactive, discussion-driven sessions. Another notable recommendation was the complete removal of the program ($f = 5$), as some participants found it ineffective and unnecessary. Similarly, enhancing practical and interactive training ($f = 5$) was emphasized, with teachers expressing the need for more classroom-based, hands-on training and interactive workshops instead of traditional lecture-style presentations. Reducing bureaucratic burden ($f = 4$) was another critical concern, with participants calling for eliminating candidate teacher files, evaluation forms, and excessive paperwork deemed unnecessary and wasteful. Additionally, reducing workload and duration ($f = 4$) was suggested, with respondents proposing a lighter teaching load for novice teachers to allow more focus on professional development and advocating for shorter program duration. Providing subject-specific and updated content ($f = 3$) was also highlighted, as participants stressed the importance of including more relevant topics, such as classroom management and material development, particularly for language teachers. Moreover, offering face-to-face training ($f = 1$) was suggested as an alternative to online instruction to improve engagement and learning outcomes. Lastly, improving mentor support and expanding school observations ($f = 1$) was recommended, with participants advocating for more opportunities to observe experienced teachers across different schools.

Table 3.
The suggested changes to the induction program

Codes	N	f
Replacing trainers and training methods	29	6
No program at all	29	5
Enhancing practical and interactive training	29	5
Reducing bureaucratic burden	29	4
Reducing workload and duration	29	4
Providing subject-specific and updated content	29	3
Offering face-to-face training	29	1
Improving mentor support and school observations	29	1

3.2. The Professional Development Needs of Novice EFL Teachers in Türkiye

The findings from Table 4 and Table 5 reveal key professional development needs shared among novice EFL teachers, experienced EFL teachers, and EFL teacher educators. These needs can be categorized into two distinct groups: in-class professional needs and out-of-class professional needs.

Table 4.

In-class professional support needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye

Statements	Novice	Experienced	Teacher Educators
Providing and maintaining classroom discipline	Some need (%41.4)	Very strong need (%69.1)	Some need (%56)
Teaching English at schools with inadequate teaching materials	Very strong need (%41.4)	Very strong need (%69.1)	Some need (%48)
Teaching English in large classes	Very strong need (%44.8)	Very strong need (%81.8)	Very strong need (%56)
Teaching English in classes of learners of low L2 proficiency	Very strong need (%44.8)	Very strong need (%78.2)	Some need (%56)
Teaching English to unmotivated learners	Very strong need (%41.4)	Very strong need (%69.1)	Very strong need (%52)
Teaching English in mixed-ability classes	Some need (%44.8)	Very strong need (%56.4)	Very strong need (%41.4)
Adjusting for individual differences among students	Some need (%37.9)	Very strong need (%58.2)	Some need (%52)
Assessing learner performance	No need (%58.6)	Some need (%40)	Some need (%52)
Mood management when dealing with challenging students	Some need (%44.8)	Very strong need (%72.7)	Some need (%44)
Time management to catch up with the syllabus	No need (%41.4)	Some need (%50.9)	Some need (%40)
Sustaining learner motivation and interest	Very little need (%37.9)	Very strong need (%63.6)	Very strong need (%52)
Effective use of body language	No need (%55.2)	Very strong need (%52.7)	Some need (%56)
Effective use of in-class teaching materials	No need (%48.3)	Very strong need (%56.4)	Some need (%56)
Integrating cultural variety into the lessons	No need (%44.8)	Very strong need (%45.5)	Very strong need (%48)
Implementing lesson plans	No need (%51.7)	Some need (%32.7)	Some need (%44)
Teaching reading skills	No need (%37.9)	Some need (%41.8)	Some need (%52)
Teaching speaking skills	No need (%37.9)	Very strong need (%60)	Some need (%48)
Teaching listening skills	No need (%37.9)	Very strong need (%52.7)	Some need (%48)
Teaching writing skills	No need (%37.9)	Very strong need (%49.1)	Some need (%44)
Teaching grammar	No need (%34.5)	Some need (%45.5)	Some need (%44)
Teaching vocabulary	No need (%37.9)	Very strong need (%43.6)	Some need (%60)

Regarding novice EFL teachers' in-class professional support needs in Türkiye, several challenges emerged as critical across at least two participant groups, agreeing on their needs (see Table 4). Classroom management challenges are widely recognized by both experienced EFL teachers (69.1%) and EFL teacher educators (56%). Similarly, teaching in challenging classroom environments—such as teaching English in large classes (novice EFL teachers: 44.8%, experienced teachers: 81.8%, teacher educators: 56%), in mixed ability classes (experienced teachers: 56.4%, teacher educators: 41.4%), and at schools with inadequate teaching materials (experienced teachers: 69.1%, novice teachers: 41.4%)—is a shared concern. Student-related challenges, including addressing unmotivated learners (novice EFL teachers: 41.4%, experienced teachers: 69.1%, teacher educators: 52%) along with sustaining student motivation and interest (experienced teachers: 63.6%, teacher educators: 52%) and low L2 proficiency levels (novice teachers: 44.8%, experienced teachers: 78.2%), are also seen as pressing issues. Furthermore, the effective use of instructional materials was identified as a significant need, with experienced teachers (56.4%) and teacher educators (56%) emphasizing its importance. Similarly, integrating cultural diversity into lessons emerged as another critical need, highlighted by experienced teachers (45.5%) and teacher educators (48%).

As to the out-of-class professional needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye (see Table 5), notably, the use of technological tools in teaching was identified as an extreme need by both experienced teachers (63.6%) and teacher educators (44%). In comparison, novice teachers essentially reported no need (51.7%). While acknowledging the importance of these challenges, teacher educators emphasized the need for professional growth in developing and adapting teaching materials (56%) and engaging in reflective practice (52%).

Table 5.

Out-of-class professional support needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye

Statements	Novice	Experienced	Teacher Educators
Preparing exams	No need (%51.7)	Some need (%30.9)	Some need (%48)
Communicating with parents	No need (%51.7)	Very strong need (%49.1)	Some need (%48)
Building relationships with colleagues	No need (%62.1)	Some need (%43.6)	Some need (%52)
Communicating with the principle	No need (%62.1)	Some need (%40)	Some need (%60)
Creating lesson plans	No need (%48.3)	Some need (%38.2)	Some need (%36)
Developing and adapting teaching materials	No need (%37.9)	Some need (%43.6)	Very strong need (%56)
Engaging in reflective practice as a teacher	Very little need (%34.5)	Some need (%50.9)	Very strong need (%52)
To be able to use technological tools effectively in teaching	No need (%51.7)	Very strong need (%63.6)	Very strong need (%44)

The qualitative analysis of participants' responses to open-ended questions reveals significant variations in the perceived support needed in induction or e-PD programs for novice Turkish EFL teachers, as shown in Table 6. Classroom management and learner engagement support emerged as a critical concern across all groups. However, experienced teachers ($f=4$) and

teacher educators (f=3) placed a stronger emphasis on this area compared to novice teachers (f=1). Similarly, administrative and bureaucratic support was widely recognized, with experienced teachers (f=6) identifying it as a particularly critical issue. Pedagogical and instructional support was the most frequently mentioned category, with experienced teachers (f=8) prioritizing it the most, followed by novice teachers (f=5) and teacher educators (f=3). The need for mentoring and professional development (PD) support was also commonly recognized, with teacher educators (f=5) emphasizing its importance more than the other groups. In terms of emotional and psychological support, experienced teachers (f=8) expressed the highest concern, while both novice teachers (f=1) and teacher educators (f=3) also acknowledged its importance. Notably, the realities of the teaching profession were a concern for both novice (f=2) and experienced teachers (f=3), but teacher educators did not address this. Ethics of the profession was only mentioned by experienced teachers (f=2), while equity, inclusion, and social justice received moderate attention from experienced teachers (f=2) and teacher educators (f=2) but not from novice teachers. Additionally, technology and online teaching were recognized as necessary support areas by experienced teachers (f=4) and teacher educators (f=2) but not by novice teachers. Finally, project and career development were only highlighted by experienced teachers (f=3), indicating that this concern grows in relevance with increased teaching experience.

Table 6.
The expected support from an e-PD program

Codes	Novice (N=29)	Experienced (N=55)	Teacher Educators (N=25)
Classroom Management & Learner Engagement	✓ 1	✓ 4	✓ 3
Administrative & Bureaucratic Support	✓ 3	✓ 6	✓ 3
Pedagogical & Instructional Support	✓ 5	✓ 8	✓ 3
Mentoring & PD Support	✓ 4	✓ 6	✓ 5
Emotional & Psychological Support	✓ 1	✓ 8	✓ 3
Realities of Teaching Profession	✓ 2	✓ 3	–
Ethics of the Profession	–	✓ 2	–
Equity, Inclusion, & Social Justice	–	✓ 2	✓ 2
Technology & Online Teaching	–	✓ 4	✓ 2
Project & Career Development	–	✓ 3	–

Table 7 provides a detailed breakdown of each category, illustrating the distinct areas of perceived support required by novice EFL teachers, experienced EFL teachers, and EFL teacher educators, with each group highlighting specific needs within the context of an e-PD program. Novice EFL teachers primarily needed support in classroom management, crisis management, and adaptation to the profession, particularly regarding motivation and psychological assistance. Experienced EFL teachers, on the other hand, focused on the need for practical support in differentiated instruction, managing large classes, and reducing bureaucratic workload. They also highlighted the importance of structured mentoring, lifelong learning, and preparation for extreme teaching conditions, such as cultural adaptation. While not explicitly mentioning some areas, such as professional ethics, EFL teacher educators focused on the importance of hands-on pedagogical experiences, differentiated instruction, and integrating technology in teaching practices. They also stressed the value of professional networking, e-mentoring, and supporting marginalized students.

Table 7.
The expected support from an e-PD program

Codes	Novice EFL Teachers need more support...	Experienced EFL Teachers emphasize the need...	EFL Teacher Educators highlight the importance of...
<i>Classroom Management & Learner Engagement</i>	in the classroom and crisis management.	for more support in the classroom and crisis management.	classroom interactional competence, learner engagement, and teaching diverse learners.
<i>Administrative & Bureaucratic Support</i>	in handling paperwork and following school procedures.	to reduce excessive bureaucratic workload.	context-specific administrative support and paperwork guidance.
<i>Pedagogical & Instructional Support</i>	in accessing quality materials, lesson planning strategies, and effective use of classroom time.	for differentiated instruction, material design, and managing large classes.	hands-on experiences, differentiated instruction, and sharing practical teaching tips.
<i>Mentoring & PD Support</i>	in the form of mentoring and networking with experienced teachers for guidance.	for structured mentoring, lifelong learning, and real classroom experiences.	e-mentoring, professional platforms, and observation-based workshops.
<i>Emotional & Psychological Support</i>	in terms of motivation and psychological assistance during their adaptation to the profession.	to prioritize motivation, stress management, and mental well-being.	the ability to cope with the emotional challenges of teaching and the affective scaffolding.
<i>Realities of Teaching Profession</i>	in handling real-life challenges in teaching.	for being prepared for extreme conditions (e.g., remote areas, cultural adaptation).	Not explicitly mentioned
<i>Ethics of the Profession</i>	Not explicitly mentioned	for having professional ethics, teacher attitude, and appropriate conduct.	Not explicitly mentioned
<i>Equity, Inclusion, & Social Justice</i>	Not explicitly mentioned	for more student-centered teaching.	supporting marginalized students and incorporating diversity in teaching.
<i>Technology & Online Teaching</i>	Not explicitly mentioned	for training on Web 2.0 tools, online material development, and digital teaching methods.	further support for online teaching methods and accessibility training.
<i>Project & Career Development</i>	Not explicitly mentioned	integrating international projects like Erasmus+ and eTwinning.	encouraging teachers to engage in professional networking and career development.

4. Discussion

Finally, this section interprets the findings in light of existing research, drawing meaningful conclusions about their significance and implications. The study provides valuable insights into novice EFL teachers' perspectives on the induction program by the Turkish MoNE and their professional development needs, as seen by themselves, experienced EFL teachers, and EFL teacher educators. The findings reveal both the strengths and shortcomings of the current program and identify key areas where novice teachers need additional support.

The study reveals that although most novice teachers engaged in induction activities, the program's effectiveness remains uncertain. In line with prior studies (Ekinçi et al., 2019;

Kozikoğlu & Soyalp, 2018; Ulubey, 2018), one notable strength identified by participants was the inclusion of information on school regulations and policies. Additionally, collegial support and mentoring were commonly reported, reinforcing previous research that emphasizes the role of mentoring in the successful transition of novices and attaining professional skills (Akyıldız et al., 2020; Çelik & Atik, 2020). However, the relatively low percentage of novices receiving subject-specific mentoring reveals a misalignment between mentorship practices and the actual instructional needs of novice teachers. This gap underscores the importance of careful mentor selection and comprehensive mentor training, as emphasized by previous studies (Akyıldız et al., 2020; Çelik & Atik, 2020; Çobanoğlu & Ayvaz-Tuncel, 2018; Ekinci et al., 2019). Effective mentoring and induction programs are crucial in supporting novice teachers during their transition into the profession, fostering their confidence, problem-solving skills, and job satisfaction while also reducing turnover (Darling-Hammond, 2003; Fantilli & McDougall, 2009; Ingersoll & Smith, 2004). However, for such programs to be effective, they must be well-structured, featuring qualified mentors and appropriate mentor-mentee matches. The success of mentoring initiatives also depends on proper training for mentors and a supportive school environment (Kardos & Johnson, 2005; Hobson et al., 2009). The findings also reveal significant shortcomings in the induction program, particularly regarding ineffective training, excessive paperwork, and an overwhelming workload. Consistent with previous studies (Akyıldız et al., 2020; Çelik & Atik, 2020; Çobanoğlu & Ayvaz-Tuncel, 2018), this study also highlights that novice teachers perceived induction program seminars as unengaging and ineffective. Participants attributed this ineffectiveness to poor planning, overly long sessions, and a predominantly theoretical approach that lacked practical relevance, ultimately failing to address their professional needs. Furthermore, the findings support previous research indicating that the excessive amount of paperwork required in induction programs presents a significant challenge for novice teachers (Altıntaş & Görgeç, 2017; Çobanoğlu & Ayvaz-Tuncel, 2018; Dursun et al., 2018; Ekinci et al., 2019). Participants reported that completing numerous forms added to their workload and limited their ability to focus on essential aspects of professional development. Consistent with Akyıldız et al. (2020), this study further reveals that administrative burdens hindered candidates from effectively observing classes, restricting opportunities for meaningful engagement in instructional practices.

The findings highlight critical areas for improvement in the induction program, emphasizing the need for structural and methodological revisions to enhance its effectiveness. The most frequently suggested change involved replacing trainers and modifying training methods, with participants advocating for more knowledgeable trainers and interactive, discussion-driven sessions rather than passive seminar-based instruction. As Gagen and Bowie (2005) point out, “Experienced teachers are often recruited as mentors without considering whether or not they have available time or have previous preparation” (p. 41). So, providing proper training for mentors is crucial, a point also emphasized by Akcan (2016). A particularly striking finding is that a notable number of participants perceived no strengths in the induction program, with some even advocating for its complete removal, citing its perceived ineffectiveness. Similarly, calls for more practical and interactive training underscore the necessity of classroom-based, hands-on experiences and workshops that better align with teachers’ professional needs, which is confirmed by prior research (Çobanoğlu & Ayvaz-Tuncel, 2018; Dursun et al., 2018; Ekinci et al., 2019). Reducing bureaucratic burden, as also recommended by previous studies (Akyıldız et al., 2020; Dursun et al., 2018; Ekinci et al., 2019), was another notable concern, as participants criticized excessive paperwork requirements, including candidate teacher files and evaluation forms, which they found unnecessary. Alongside these suggestions, reducing workload and program duration was also

proposed to allow novice teachers more time to focus on professional development. This suggestion was mirrored (Çobanoğlu & Ayvaz-Tuncel, 2018) in the existing literature. The need for subject-specific and updated content was particularly emphasized by novice EFL teachers, who requested more relevant topics such as classroom management and material development. While less frequently mentioned, offering face-to-face training instead of online instruction was suggested to enhance engagement, and improving mentor support with expanded school observations was recommended to provide novice teachers with greater exposure to diverse teaching practices. Collectively, considering the level of dissatisfaction and the findings of the study, a more relevant, practical, engaging, and tailored induction program and professional development opportunities that better support novice teachers' professional growth are needed.

The professional development needs of novice EFL teachers in Türkiye were explored through insights gathered from novice EFL teachers, as well as experienced EFL teachers and EFL teacher educators, to gain a comprehensive understanding. An interesting finding from the descriptive statistics is that classroom management support is viewed as a significant need only by experienced EFL teachers. In contrast, novice EFL teachers and teacher educators acknowledged only a moderate need for support in maintaining discipline. This finding contrasts with existing literature, which identifies classroom management as one of the top challenges novice teachers face (e.g., Fantilli & McDougall, 2009; Farrell, 2012; Onafowora, 2005; Wolff et al., 2017). However, qualitative data suggests that EFL teacher educators also recognize the need for classroom management support. Research (e.g., Wolff, 2017) has shown that expert and novice teachers differ significantly in how they notice (perceive) and interpret (make sense of) classroom events, so this discrepancy may indicate that novice teachers, lacking experience, do not yet perceive specific instructional challenges as critical, while experienced teachers, having faced these issues over time, express a more urgent need for effective pedagogical and classroom management strategies.

Furthermore, while all stakeholders shared concerns about teaching in challenging environments—such as large classes and unmotivated learners—additional challenges like teaching English to learners with low L2 proficiency, working in schools with inadequate teaching materials, managing mixed-ability classes, and sustaining learner motivation were identified by at least two stakeholders. The qualitative data further highlights the need for pedagogical support, including differentiated instruction, managing large classes, and navigating the realities of teaching. Additionally, there is a noted demand for emotional and psychological support, encompassing motivation, stress management, well-being, and affective scaffolding, which Karanfil and Atay (2020) also emphasized. Although descriptive statistics showed that novice teachers did not recognize a need for additional support in using in-class materials or developing and adapting teaching materials—areas identified as critical by experienced teachers and teacher educators—qualitative data indicates a desire for access to high-quality materials. While acknowledging the importance of these challenges, teacher educators emphasized the need for professional growth in developing and adapting teaching materials, engaging in reflective practice, and integrating cultural diversity into lessons. These findings suggest that classroom management and student engagement are central concerns for in-service teachers, and teacher educators prioritize skill development in instructional design and self-reflection. The emphasis on reflective practice aligns with Stewart and Jansky's (2022) recommendation to design professional development programs that encourage novice teachers to reflect on the specific challenges they face in their teaching environments. In line with Schön's (1987) concept of reflection-on-action, this approach advocates for analyzing challenges after they occur, transforming the induction process into

an ongoing inquiry cycle. Research further supports the role of systematic reflection in teacher development, with scholars such as Güngör et al. (2019) and Karataş and Karaman (2013) advocating for structured reflective practices. Likewise, Farrell (2012) believes that novice teachers should be motivated to engage in structured reflection on their teaching practices. This can be facilitated by in-depth examination and analysis of their beliefs, teaching methods, critical incidents, and case studies.

Research highlights the strong link between resilience and reflective practice in teaching. Reflection is crucial in teacher education, mentorship, and development programs, helping educators build adaptive and effective pedagogies. Tailored mentoring supports critical reflective practice by refining teachers' ability to notice, clarify, and interpret classroom experiences, ultimately fostering professional growth (Kutsyuruba et al., 2019). Ongoing reflective practice might ensure that professional development is responsive to the evolving needs of novice teachers in Türkiye. As Day and Gu (2007, pp. 439-440) assert, "responsive and differentiated support to meet teachers' professional and personal learning needs at different times in their work and lives can help counter declining commitment trajectories, enhancing the continuity of positive development of teachers' professional commitment and, thus, their effectiveness." Therefore, to develop a professional development program that effectively addresses the needs of novice EFL teachers, these findings, supported by the literature, underscore the importance of including key components that are well-being, classroom management, materials development integrated with technology, handling diversity in EFL classrooms, and reflective practice.

5. Conclusion and Implications

In conclusion, this study explores novice EFL teachers' perceived professional development needs in Türkiye by gathering insights from multiple stakeholders with varying experience levels, offering diverse perspectives. It also examines novice teachers' perceptions of the induction program implemented by the Turkish MoNE. The findings reveal that while most novice teachers participated in induction activities, the program's overall effectiveness remains uncertain. While it provided valuable information on school regulations and policies and facilitated novice teachers' transition into the profession, key shortcomings were identified, including insufficient subject-specific mentoring, excessive paperwork, heavy workloads, gaps in classroom management support, pedagogical training, and strategies for teaching low-proficiency learners. Additionally, the need for emotional and psychological support, such as stress management and teacher well-being, was emphasized. These findings suggest that professional development programs should adopt a more tailored, practical, and interactive approach to meet novice teachers' evolving needs better.

This study carries important implications for policymakers, teacher educators, and school administrators. The findings indicate that the current induction program requires structural and methodological revisions to enhance its effectiveness. Specifically, mentor selection and training should be improved, ensuring mentors are qualified and willing to participate. The administrative workload associated with the program should also be reduced, allowing novice teachers to focus on meaningful professional development. Increasing classroom time and practical experiences would further contribute to their growth. For teacher educators, integrating reflective practice into teacher education programs could help novices critically analyze their teaching experiences, refine instructional strategies, and build resilience in the face of professional challenges. School administrators should foster a supportive work

environment at the institutional level, providing ongoing mentorship, peer collaboration, and classroom-based learning opportunities for novice teachers.

Despite its contributions, this study is not without limitations. First, while the sample included a diverse group of participants from various regions in Türkiye, the reliance on self-reported data may have introduced biases, as participants' perceptions may not entirely reflect their actual experiences. Future research could address this limitation by incorporating observational methods or longitudinal studies to provide a more comprehensive understanding of novice teachers' professional development trajectories. Additionally, expanding the participant pool would enhance the generalizability of the results. Furthermore, including perspectives from school administrators and mentor teachers would offer further insights into the effectiveness of induction and professional development programs. Future studies should consider incorporating these viewpoints to present a more holistic view of the challenges and support mechanisms available to novice teachers. Given the limited number of studies on this topic, future research could explore this area using varied data collection methods and including diverse participant groups.

Ethical Issues

This paper is based on the first author's doctoral dissertation supervised by the second author at the Graduate School of Educational Sciences, Hacettepe University in Ankara, Turkey. The authors confirm that ethical approval was obtained from Hacettepe University (Approval Date: 29/07/2021) with decision number 1678079.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Akcan, S. (2016). Novice non-native English teachers' reflections on their teacher education programmes and their first years of teaching. *Profile Issues in Teachers Professional Development*, 18(1), 55–70. <https://doi.org/10.15446/profile.v18n1.48608>
- Akçor, G., & Savaşçı, M. (2020). A review of challenges and recommendations for novice EFL teachers in Turkey. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 14(2), 16–37.
- Akyıldız, S., Altun, T., & Kasım, Ş. (2020). Adaylık eğitimi uygulama sürecinin aday öğretmenlerin görüşlerine göre incelenmesi. *IBAD Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 6, 117–131. <https://doi.org/10.21733/ibad.655108>
- Anhorn, R. (2008). The profession that eats its young. *Delta Kappa Gamma Bulletin*, 74(3), 15–21.
- Bekdemir, N. (2019). *Adaptation problems and solutions of novice teachers of English*. (ID 564407) [MA Thesis, Hacettepe University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center.
- Bulut Albaba, M. (2017). Teacher learning during transition from pre-service to novice EFL teacher: A longitudinal case study. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 11(2), 142–154.
- Chaaban, Y., & Du, X. (2017). Novice teachers' job satisfaction and coping strategies: Overcoming contextual challenges at Qatari government schools. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 67, 340–350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.07.002>
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education*. New York: Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.

- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Çakmak, M., Gündüz, M., & Emstad, A. B. (2018). Challenging moments of novice teachers: survival strategies developed through experiences. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 49(2), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764x.2018.1476465>
- Çelik, O., T., & Atik, S. (2020). Prospective teacher training program in Turkey: A meta-synthesis study. *Journal of Qualitative Research in Education*, 8(2), 539–564. <https://doi.org/10.14689/issn.2148-624.1.8c.2s.6m>
- Çobanoğlu, F., & Ayvaz-Tuncel, Z. (2018). Teacher induction program: First experience in Turkey. *International Education Studies*, 11(6), 99–108. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v11n6p99>
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2003). Keeping good teachers: Why it matters, what leaders can do. *Educational leadership*, 60(8), 6–13.
- Day, C., & Gu, Q. (2007). Variations in the conditions for teachers' professional learning and development: Sustaining commitment and effectiveness over a career. *Oxford Review of Education*, 33(4), 423–443. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054980701450746>
- Dursun, F., Yenen, E. T., & Bulut, A. (2018). Aday öğretmen yetiştirme sürecine yönelik aday ve danışman öğretmenlerin görüşleri. *Maarif Mektepleri Uluslararası Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2(2), 1–17.
- Ekinci, A., Bozan, S., & Sakız, H. (2019). Aday öğretmen yetiştirme programının etkililiğine ilişkin aday ve danışman öğretmen görüşlerinin değerlendirilmesi. *Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Fakültesi Dergisi*, 52(3), 801–836. <https://doi.org/10.30964/aebfd.466469>
- Ergünay, O., & Adıgüzel, O. C. (2019). Aday öğretmenlerin ilk yıl mesleki deneyimleri sürecinde karşılaştıkları sorun ve kaynakları. *Eğitimde Nitel Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 7(3), 1080–1099. <https://doi.org/10.14689/issn.2148-624.1.7c.3s.8m>
- Fantilli, R. D., & McDougall, D. E. (2009). A study of novice teachers: Challenges and supports in the first years. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 25(6), 814–825. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2009.02.021>
- Farrell, T. S. (2003). Learning to teach English language during the first year: Personal influences and challenges. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 19(1), 95–111. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(02\)00088-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(02)00088-4)
- Farrell, T. S. (2006). The first year of language teaching: Imposing order. *System*, 34(2), 211–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2005.12.001>
- Farrell, T. S. (2012). Novice-service language teacher development: Bridging the gap between preservice and in-service education and development. *TESOL Quarterly*, 46(3), 435–449. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.36>
- Farrell, T. S. (2016). Surviving the transition shock in the first year of teaching through reflective practice. *System*, 61, 12–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2016.07.005>
- Feiman-Nemser, S. (2001). Helping novices learn to teach: Lessons from an exemplary support teacher. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 52(1), 17–30. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487101052001003>
- Gagen, L., & Bowie, S. (2005). Effective mentoring: A case for training mentors for novice teachers. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 76(7), 40–45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07303084.2005.10609312>
- Gok Kaca, G., & Yigitoglu, N. (2017). Influences of instructional policies on novice teacher cognition: Help or a hindrance? *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 42(9), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2017v42n9.1>

- Güngör, M. N., Akcan, S., Werbinska, D., & Ekiert, M. (2019). The early years of teaching: A cross-cultural study of Turkish and Polish novice English teachers. *Eurasian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 5(2), 287–302. <https://doi.org/10.32601/ejal.599262>
- Hebert, E., & Worthy, T. (2001). Does the first year of teaching have to be a bad one? A case study of success. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(8), 897–911. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(01\)00039-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(01)00039-7)
- Hobson, A. J., Ashby, P., Malderez, A., & Tomlinson, P. D. (2009). Mentoring beginning teachers: What we know and what we don't. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 25(1), 207–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2008.09.001>
- Hong, J. Y. (2012). Why do some beginning teachers leave the school, and others stay? Understanding teacher resilience through psychological lenses. *Teachers and Teaching*, 18(4), 417–440. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2012.696044>
- İlyas, İ. E., Coşkun, İ., & Toklucu, D. (2017). *Türkiye'de aday öğretmen yetiştirme modeli: İzleme ve değerlendirme*. İstanbul: SETA Yayınları. Retrieved from <https://setav.org/assets/uploads/2017/04/AdayOgretmenler.pdf>
- Ingersoll, R. M., & Smith, T. M. (2004). Do teacher induction and mentoring matter? *NASSP Bulletin*, 88(638), 28–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/019263650408863803>
- Karanfil, F., & Atay, D. (2020). The well-being of novice state school teachers in the mentoring programme in Turkey: A narrative inquiry. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 9(1), 56–67. <https://doi.org/10.34293/education.v9i1.3438>
- Karataş, P., & Karaman, A. C. (2013). Challenges faced by novice language teachers: Support, identity, and pedagogy in the initial years of teaching. *The International Journal of Research in Teacher Education*, 4(3), 10–23.
- Kardos, S. M., & Johnson, S. M. (2010). New teachers' experiences of mentoring: The good, the bad, and the inequity. *Journal of Educational Change*, 11(1), 23–44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-008-9096-4>
- Kennedy, A., & McKay, J. (2011). Beyond induction: The continuing professional development needs of early-career teachers in Scotland. *Professional Development in Education*, 37(4), 551–569. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2010.533598>
- Kim, K. A., & Roth, G. L. (2011). Novice teachers and their acquisition of work-related information. *Current Issues in Education*, 14(1), 1–25.
- Kozikoğlu, İ., & Senemoğlu, N. (2018). Mesleğe yeni başlayan öğretmenlerin karşılaştıkları güçlükler: Nitel bir çözümleme. *Eğitimde Nitel Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 6(3), 341–371. <https://doi.org/10.14689/issn.2148-2624.1.6c3s16m>
- Kozikoğlu, İ., & Soyaloğlu, H. (2018). Aday öğretmenlerin, danışman öğretmenlerin ve okul yöneticilerinin aday öğretmen yetiştirme programına yönelik görüşlerinin incelenmesi. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 33(4), 934–952. <https://doi.org/10.16986/HUJE.2018037027>
- Kutsyuruba, B., Walker, K. D., Stasel, R. S., & Makhamreh, M. A. (2019). Developing resilience and promoting well-being in early career teaching. *Canadian Journal of Education/Revue canadienne de l'éducation*, 42(1), 285–321.
- Lomi, A. N. K., & Mbato, C. L. (2020). Struggles and strategies in constructing professional identity: The first-year teaching experiences of Indonesian EFL novice teachers. *Journal of English Education and Teaching*, 4(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.33369/jeet.4.1.1-19>
- Onafowora, L. L. (2005). Teacher efficacy issues in the practice of novice teachers. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 28(4), 34–43.
- Öztürk, M. (2008). *Induction into teaching: Adaptation challenges of novice teachers*. (ID 227639). [MA Thesis, Middle East Technical University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center.

- Öztürk, M., & Yıldırım, A. (2012). English as a foreign language instructors' induction: Early practices of language teachers teaching at tertiary level. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 3(2), 1–17.
- Sali, P., & Kecik, I. (2018). Challenges of first years of teaching in Turkey: Voices of novice EFL teachers. *English Language Teaching*, 11(4), 117–131. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v11n4p117>
- Sali, P. (2008). *Novice EFL teachers' perceived challenges and support needs in their journey to become effective teachers*. (ID 229223). [Doctoral dissertation, Anadolu University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center.
- Schön, D. A. (1987). *Educating the reflective practitioner*. USA: Jossey-Bass.
- Septiani, A., Emiliasari, R. N., & Rofli, A. (2019). The novice English teachers' experience: practices and challenges. *Academic Journal Perspective: Education, Language, and Literature*, 7(2), 109–118. <https://doi.org/10.33603/perspective.v7i2.2708>
- Smith, T. M., & Ingersoll, R. M. (2004). What are the effects of induction and mentoring on beginning teacher turnover? *American Educational Research Journal*, 41(3), 681–714. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312041003681>
- Stewart, T. T., & Jansky, T. A. (2022). Novice teachers and embracing struggle: Dialogue and reflection in professional development. *Teaching and Teacher Education: Leadership and Professional Development*, 1, 100002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tatep.2022.100002>
- Stewart, T. T., Hill, J., & Lindstrom, P. N. (2020). Exploring wobble through collaborative dialogue to reconcile theory and practice. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 47(1), 48–70.
- Ulubey, O. (2018). Evaluation of novice teacher training program. *Hacettepe University Journal of Education*, 33(2), 480–502. <https://doi.org/10.16986/HUJE.2017031014>
- Veenman, S. (1984). Perceived problems of beginning teachers. *Review of Educational Research*, 54(2), 143–178. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543054002143>
- Widiati, U., Suryati, N., & Hayati, N. (2018). Unraveling the challenges of Indonesian novice teachers of English. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 7(3), 621–629. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v7i3.9824>
- Wilson, V., Hall, J., Davidson, J., & Lewin, J. (2006). *Developing teachers: A review of early professional learning*. The SCORE Centre, Faculty of Education, University of Glasgow.
- Wolff, C. E., Jarodzka, H., & Boshuizen, H. P. (2017). See and tell: Differences between expert and novice teachers' interpretations of problematic classroom management events. *Teaching and teacher education*, 66, 295–308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.04.015>
- Zein, M. S. (2017). Professional development needs of primary EFL teachers: Perspectives of teachers and teacher educators. *Professional Development in Education*, 43(2), 293–313. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2016.1156013>
- Zepeda, S. J., & Mayers, R. S. (2001). New kids on the block schedule: Beginning teachers face challenges. *The High School Journal*, 84(4), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1353/hsj.2001.0014>
- Zhukova, O. (2018). Novice teachers' concerns, early professional experiences and development: Implications for theory and practice. *Discourse and Communication for Sustainable Education*, 9(1), 100–114. <https://doi.org/10.2478/dcse-2018-0008>
- Zorba, M. G. (2022). Exploring novice English teachers' professional development: Insights from the Turkish context. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 15(1), 446–466. Retrieved from <https://ijci.net/index.php/IJCI/article/view/1232>